

THE STRATEGIC HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT ON STRATEGIC INTELLIGENCE (A CASE STUDY: AL HIKMA PHARMACEUTICALS, JORDAN)

¹AMJED ALFITYANI and ²HAKAM MAALI

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Accounting, Faculty of Business, Applied Science Private University.

²Business Department, Al Istiqlal University, Jericho, Palestine.

Abstract

The study aims to examine The Strategic Human Resource Management on Strategic Intelligence of Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan. The study argues that the importance of human resources management systems in industrial companies in general, and pharmaceutical companies in particular, is an attempt to identify the impact of human resource management strategies on strategic intelligence, with the impact of human resources management systems. The independent variable is strategic human resource management and the dependent variable is strategic intelligence which consist of (Systemic Thinking, Future Vision, and Motivation). The data collected from 200 responses at al Hikma Company distributed as a questionnaire and the results shown rejected the hypotheses of the study.

Introduction

The information systems are the main source of decision-making, some describe it as the engine fuel, and everyone - institutions and individuals - assert that computer technology and information play an essential role in solving administrative problems, which have become more complex. As a result, In order to transform the traditional administrative activities to be managed by the latest technology (Al-Gasawneh et al., 2022) in accordance with computerized management systems, this has an impact on the speed and quality of work (Ismail, 2011). One of the most important tasks that affects the status of the institution in the market, and represents the decision-making process, especially with regard to strategic decisions, (alfityani at al, 2022) the circumstances and variables that accompanied the diversity and restriction in the factors of the environment of internal and external organizations of business, necessitated the presence of intelligent leaders and intellectuals with unconventional skills based (Al-Gasawneh, J, et al., 2021) on the basis of knowledge development Experience and principles, and the formation of visions related to the future and ways to confront the present, through the adoption of appropriate scientific methods, through which the future can be prepared to face the various developments and changes, and hence emerged the concept of strategic intelligence, I of intelligence to reconcile it with other intelligence patterns (Ali, 2015). Given the implications of globalization, privatization, information technology and the digital economy, various business organizations find themselves governed by competitive advantage and the struggle for survival, (Mansur et al, 2022) they have major commitments in decision-making. Decision-making in a business organization should be based on scientific methodology to a number of technical tools and techniques, which rationalize decisions, and achieve the best results that ensure the distinction of the Organization among other organizations operating in the market

itself, and today we need the most strategic intelligence, to develop solutions to the case of repetition and inertia and pattern And identify new mechanisms for action by organizations (Imran, 2015). The companies apply human resources management systems in order to achieve organizational performance, moreover, the objectives of human resources management system are to lower administrative costs, increase productivity, speed response times, improve decision-making, and enhance customer service all at the same time (Tesi, 2010). While the state of the reviewed literature provides (Houda aleqedat, et al., 2022)

Statement of the Problem

As a result, In order to transform the traditional administrative activities to be managed by the latest technology in accordance with computerized management systems, this has an impact on the speed and quality of work (Ismail, 2011). One of the most important tasks that affects the status of the institution in the market, and represents the decision-making process, (Al-Gasawneh et al., 2021) especially with regard to strategic decisions, the circumstances and variables that accompanied the diversity and restriction in the factors of the environment of internal and external organizations of business (Ali, 2015).

The problem of the study is related to the role of human resource management system on strategic human resource management.

Objectives of the study:

Based on the research problem and the scope of the study, the research questions are as follows:

- Does strategic human resource management affect strategic intelligence in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan?
- Is there any significant impact of strategic human resource management on systematic thinking in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan?
- Is there any significant impact of strategic human resource management on future vision in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan?
- Is there any significant impact of strategic human resource management on motivation in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan?

Objectives of the Study

Based on the questions illustrated in the previous section, the objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To examine the impact of strategic human resource management on strategic intelligence in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan.
2. To investigate the impact of strategic human resource management on systematic thinking in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan.

3. To assess if there is any significant impact of strategic human resource management on future vision in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan.
4. To study the impact of strategic human resource management on motivaztion in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jorda

Hypotheses of the Study

Based on the research questions and the research objectives, following are the hypotheses of the study:

- H₀1:** There is no significant impact of strategic human resource management on strategic intelligence in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan.
- H₀2:** There is no significant impact of strategic human resource management on systematic thinking in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan.
- H₀3:** There is no significant impact of strategic human resource management on future vision in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan.
- H₀4:** There is no significant impact of strategic human resource management on motivation in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan.
- H₀5:** There is no significant moderating effect of human resource management system on the impact of strategic human resource management on strategic intelligence in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan.

Independent variable

Dependant variable

Review of Literature

Al-Gasawneh, J., et al (2020) investigates the relationship between strategic intelligence dimensions which are: (Visioning, Foresight, Partnership, Intuition, and Creativity) and organizational agility achieve in the Mining and Extraction Industries sector in Jordan. The study used questionnaire for collecting data from (15) companies. The study found that all the strategic intelligence dimensions (Visioning, Foresight, Partnership, Intuition, and Creativity) effect organizational agility achieve, but the influence was more on dimensional creativity, the study reported that managers of mining and extraction industries companies need to better understand how to evaluate, identify organizational agility. **Keikha et. al. (2016)** investigate

that relationship between strategic intelligence and the performance of employees in private banks of Zahedan in Iran. The study results indicated that strategic intelligence and all its dimensions such as “competitive intelligence, business intelligence and knowledge management” have a great relationship and impacts employees' organizational performance in private banks. The study also found that “competitive intelligence, business intelligence and knowledge management” have the ability to predict the performance of their employees also the causal impact of strategic intelligence on employees' performance has a satisfactory level of appropriateness as results show.

Imran (2015) examines the impact of strategic intelligence (Prospective, system thinking, strategic vision, partnership, motivation and intuition) on organizational innovation. The study found that strategic intelligence in all its dimension impact in achieving creative ability to the company researched. The study also reported that studied company “AsiaCell” has made to take advantage of the experience and skill of its manager think about the impact of mature thinking creative while there was a failure to invest in the company researched the principle of partnership with. **Sabrina (2015)** investigates the impact of human resources development strategy on the performance of individuals in universities. The study concluded that training, organizational learning, organizational development, management, career development and creativity represent important strategies adopted by the universities in the development of human resources of administrative staff professors. The study stressed that despite the importance of strategies: Organizational development, development of the career path and creativity in the development and improvement of the human element in the universities under study, and its role in raising the levels of performance; but there are some shortcomings in the practices of this strategy, which reduced some of its effectiveness. **Atta (2015)** explained the strategic elements of strategic intelligence that represent the variables of stability, withdrawal strategy, integration strategy, product development strategy and market penetration strategy. Data were collected for the completion of the study by distributing a questionnaire to a sample of 52 officials at the level of senior administrative leaders. The results of the data analysis resulted in the following: There is a clear interest by the company's strategy development by improving the quality of products. The results proved the existence of a correlation and the impact of significant strategic intelligence in determining the strategic option. **Yahiaoui et. al. (2015)** review the process of HRM in private and public organizations, and it relation with performance. The study found that there are differences between human resources in the public and private sectors. But the goal is the same to enable our organizations to attract, develop and retain talent. The study reported that one key difference is that, unlike the private sector, most public sector organizations are not at-will employers. Among other things, that means that employees can only be removed "for cause." There are several reasons for that, including court rulings that government employees have property rights to their jobs and therefore this property their jobs can only be taken away for cause. **Shaikh (2015)** explains the emerging trends in HRM. The study reported that traditional functions of HRM now need to be strategically directed towards developing and sustaining organizational capabilities, through activities that overlap with traditional business functions such as finance, marketing, and non-traditional activities, such acknowledge management. The study also reported that HRM has the

responsibility to maximize efficiency and profit, but in the emerging scenario, the role of HR manager is changing rapidly due to changes in government policies, unions, labor legislations and technology. The trends is taken place in the organization, job design, motivation, human resource planning, recruitment, and skill development and employee relations. **Ali et. al. (2015)** analyzed the relationship of Strategic HRM practices with organizational performance and employee relations climate in banking sector of Pakistan. The study also tested the moderating effects of gender between SHRM practices and employee relations climate. The result reveals that gender moderates the relationship of SHRM practices with employee relations climate. Also SHRM practices have a positive relationship with organizational performance and employee relations climate. **Ali (2015)** clarifies the importance of strategic intelligence in the decision making process of the institution, applying to the Fertial Foundation, based on the view of the Director of the Directorate of Management in the institution, where an interview was conducted. The researcher concluded by emphasizing the hypotheses that were developed and the main hypothesis that strategic intelligence is of great importance in the decision making in the institution. The results of the interview revealed that the institution depends on applying the dimensions of strategic intelligence in the decision making process of the institution. The study also shows the difference between strategic intelligence and economic intelligence. Economic intelligence is a term that is a penalty of strategic intelligence. This kind of intelligence often leads to the availability of economic intelligence. A strategically intelligent leader will inevitably take into consideration the objectives of the economy. **Abou El Ghanem (2015)** analyzes the effect of strategic intelligence on decision-making effectiveness in the Saudi insurance companies operating in Jeddah. The study used the questionnaire which distributed to 240 employees of study sample. 185 questionnaires were recollected. The study reported that there was a strong statistical impact of strategic intelligence and its dimensions (Prospective vision, systemic thinking, partnership, and intuition) on decision-making effectiveness dimensions (problem identification, development of alternatives, choosing a suitable alternative, and implementation and Follow- up). The study also reported that insurance companies to concentrate on the elements of strategic intelligence and decision-making effectiveness. The results of the study showed the importance and the effect of strategic intelligence on decision-making effectiveness.

Type of data:

The primary sources: to address the analytical aspects of the subject. The research used preliminary data collected through a questionnaire as the main tool of research.

The accepted questionnaire for statistical analysis was (200), the response rate was (93%) for all sample. Table (1) shows the companies of Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals group in Jordan were the questionnaire was collect from which is (Hikma main site, Arabia site in salt city, Advance site in Sahab city). The respond rate reflect that the result of the study will make sense.

Table (1): Sample Size and Response Rate

NO.	Bank Name	Distributed Questionnaire	Accepted Questionnaire	Response Rate
1	Hikma Main Site	100	94	93%
2	Arabia Site in Salt City	65	63	
3	Advance Site in Sahab City	50	43	
Total		215	200	

Independent Variable: Strategic human resource management (question 1-15):

HRM Strategy (Question 1-5):

Staffing strategy is a dimension of strategic human resource management which measured by five statements and questions of Likert scale. Likert scale is organized as a five point scale which starts by strongly disagree to strongly agree. Following are the statements and questions of Likert scale that are used to measure staffing strategy:

Table 2: HRM Statements

S.NO	HRM Strategy (Question 1-5)		SD	D	N	A	SA	
1	The company develop a job description with input from the manager.	Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	5	Strongly Agree
2	The company develop a detailed and useful set of job requirements with the manager.		1	2	3	4	5	
3	The company gather skills information from employees to help you find qualified internal candidates before recruiting from outside.		1	2	3	4	5	
4	The company document turnover trends to help you predict how many people will leave an organization.		1	2	3	4	5	
5	HR staffing need to understanding the characteristics of a strategic HR function		1	2	3	4	5	

Dependent Variables: Strategic intelligence (question 16-30):

The dependent variable; strategic intelligence is further divided into three dimensions which are systematic thinking, future vision and motivation. Following is the operational definition of these dimensions:

Systemic Thinking (Question 16-20)

Systematic thinking is a dimension of the dependent variable; strategic intelligence. A five statements and questions of Likert scale are used to measure systematic thinking. The five points Likert scale is expressed as a scale which starts from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Following are the statements and questions of Likert scale that are used to measure systematic thinking:

Table 3: Systemic Thinking Statements

S.NO	Systemic Thinking (Question 16-20)	SD	D	N	A	SA
16	Well-designed human resources ensure organizational success.	1	2	3	4	5
17	Systems thinking help human resource management initiatives to ensure that all aspects of the organization are working cooperatively.	1	2	3	4	5
18	Systems thinking should be applied to organisation design and management	1	2	3	4	5
19	Systems thinking is an approach to problem-solving that sees complex entities as a series of components with each part interacting with and influencing the rest.	1	2	3	4	5
20	systems thinking shouldn't be the preserve of a select group of senior leaders	1	2	3	4	5

Future Vision (Question 21-25)

Future vision is a dimension of strategic intelligence. It is measured by five statements and questions of Likert scale. Likert scale is organized as a five point scale which starts by strongly disagree to strongly agree. Following are the statements and questions of Likert scale that are used to measure future vision:

Table 4: Future Vision Statements

S.NO	Future Vision (Question 21-25)	SD	D	N	A	SA
21	Employers are increasingly searching for innovative offerings to address their employees' demands	1	2	3	4	5
22	Vision care schemes can play a major role in employee benefit programmes.	1	2	3	4	5
23	Thorough vision company can increase employee health awareness, leading to a healthier and more productive workforce.	1	2	3	4	5
24	A vision statement describes the company as it would appear in a future successful state.	1	2	3	4	5
25	It creates a mental image of the future state that the company wishes to achieve.	1	2	3	4	5

Motivation (Question 26-30)

Motivation is a dimension of the dependent variable; strategic intelligence. A five statements and questions of Likert scale are used to measure motivation. The five points Likert scale is expressed as a scale which starts from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Following are the statements and questions of Likert scale that are used to measure motivation:

Table 5: Motivation Statements

S.NO	Motivation (Question 26-30)	Strongly Disagree	SD	D	N	A	SA	Strongly Agree
26	Motivation is one of the most important concepts in HR		1	2	3	4	5	
27	The companies spend humungous amounts of money in arranging for training sessions and recreational events to motivate the employees.		1	2	3	4	5	
28	HR managers stress on the employees having high levels of motivation to get the job done		1	2	3	4	5	
29	workplace motivation instills pride and a desire to excel		1	2	3	4	5	
30	Increasing motivation requires company to pinpoint the exact areas of needed improvement.		1	2	3	4	5	

4.6 Data Analysis and Hypothesis Testing Methods

Statistical tools used for analysing the data and testing study hypotheses are as under:

1. Working out frequency rates and percentages relevant to the questionnaire paragraphs.
2. Calculating standard deviations and mean in all questionnaire paragraphs.
3. Using the exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis.
4. Multiple regression model for testing the general hypotheses.

Limitation:

- The results of this study may not be generalized over the entire industry or pharmaceutical companies in Jordan, because it a case study on Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan. Moreover; other pharmaceutical companies not included in the study in general.
- The results of the study limited to Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co.
- The study results of the relation of human resource management system in the relationship between strategic human resource management and strategic intelligence of Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan. Therefore the results are limit to the variables that used by study.

Reliability:

The reliability test was conducted to provide evidence that instrument produced as data, for which it was designed. The reliability value gained was greater than 0.80 indicating an acceptance of research testing.

Table (6): Cronbach's Alpha for Research Variables

No.	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Item
1	HRM Strategy.	0.770	5
4	Systemic Thinking.	0.907	5
5	Future Vision.	0.971	5
6	Motivation	0.890	5
All		0.884	20

Reliability is the methods which calculate to test if the questionnaire or study tool has the ability to give the same results and if the measurement was repeated on the same person several times in the same circumstances, and reliability considered as a correlation coefficient, and are intended to link the extent of repeated readings of the measurement results and then calculation of the value of Cronbach's alpha is done. Reliability more than 70% is acceptable and those are over 80% to be good.

Descriptive statistics:

Frequencies and percentages are used to describe and explain the data. Demographic variables are presented using frequencies and percentages which demonstrated by tables and figures. Further, minimum, maximum, mean and descriptive statistics are used for the questions as well as the main variables of the study. Following is a discussion of the descriptive statistics used by this study.

Demographic Variables

As shown in table (7) the study is based on 200 respondents some of them are males and some others are females. Males make up 56.5 % of the total respondents, while females make up 43.5 %. This means that number of males respondents are little more than females ones; in other words, the study consists of 113 male respondents and 87 female respondents.

Table (7): Gender, Age education experience

Gender	NO.	%	Age	NO.	%	Experience	NO.	%	Exp.	NO.	%
Male	113.0	56.5	20-25 year old	33	16.5	PhD	9	4.5	Less than 5	26	13.0
Female	87.0	43.5	26-30 year-old	56	28.0	Masters	28	14.0	5-10 years	44	22.0
Total	200	100.0	31-35 year-old	73	36.5	Bachelor	111	55.5	10-or less than 15 years	71	35.5
			36-40 year-old	24	12.0	Diploma	37	18.5	15-or less than 20 years	38	19.0
			41 or more	14	7.0	High school	15	7.5	20 years or more	21	10.5
			Total	200	100.0	Total	200	100.0	Total	200	100.0

Table (7) demonstrates the age intervals of respondents. It is shown that there are 200 respondents with different age. The study reveals that 33 respondents are aged 20 to 25 year old, 56 respondents are aged between 26 and 30, 73 respondents are of the age between 31 and 35, 24 respondents are aged between 36 and 40, and 41 respondents are over 41 years old.

Table number (7) shows the statistic related to education. It is clear from the table that there are only 9 respondents who hold a Ph.D. degree and they are the least respondents; the majority of the respondents 111 out of 200 respondents are having a Bachelor degree; 37, 28, and 15 respondents hold Diploma, Master and High school degree respectively Table 5.1 illustrates the experience of employees who participated in the questionnaire of this study. The table shows that majority of respondents (71 employees) have experience of 10 to 15 years, 44 respondents (employees) have experience between 5 and 10 years, 38 respondents (employees) have experience between 15 to 20 years and 26 respondents (employees) have experience less than 5 years.

Descriptive statistics of the Variables:

Table (8) shows the descriptive statistics for study model variables which include independent variable which is strategic human resource management and represented by (Staffing Strategy, Developmental Strategy, Compensation Strategy) and dependent variable which is strategic intelligence and represented by (Systemic Thinking, Future Vision, Motivation) and the moderator variable which is human resource management system and represented by (Job Analysis Application, Recruitment Application, Performance Appraisal Application).

The result reveals that there are positive attitudes toward the study model in general because all variables have a positive mean and above the standard mean. The result reflects a positive attitude toward the study sample, model and all variables which can be classified according to its mean, as follows:

- 1 Systemic Thinking (M= 3.68).
- 2 Motivation (M= 3.64).
- 3 Future Vision (M= 3.50).
- 4 HRS (M= 3.48).

Table (8): Descriptive Statistics for the Study Model

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
HR Strategy.	200	1.00	5.00	3.4800	1.22355
Systemic Thinking.	200	1.00	5.00	3.6800	.93379
Future Vision.	200	1.00	5.00	3.5000	.91333
Motivation	200	1.00	5.00	3.6450	.90169

Impact of strategic human resource management (SHRM) on strategic intelligence

Table (9) provides a regression analysis of the impact of strategic human resource management on strategic intelligence. Strategic human resource management is measured by HRM strategy however, strategic intelligence is considered as a summation score of systemic thinking, future vision and motivation. This leads to **reject H₀₁** which states that “**There is no significant impact HRM strategy on strategic intelligence**”

Table (9) Multiple Regression Model of the Impact of Strategic Human Resource Management on Strategic Intelligence

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.622	.212		7.666	0.00		
HRM Strategy	.336	.041	.516	8.197	0.00***	.745	1.343
R Square							.421
Adjusted R Square							.412
Sig. F Change							0.000
Durbin-Watson							2.024

Note: *** is significant at the level of 1%,

Impact of strategic human resource management (SHRM) on systematic thinking

The results in Table (10) illustrate an estimation of regression analysis of the impact of strategic human resource management on systematic thinking. HRM strategy, is the three measures of strategic human resource management and systematic thinking is one of the dimensions of strategic intelligence. Systematic thinking is regressed and functioned by the three measures of strategic human resource management;

Accordingly H₀₂ is reject which states that “There is no significant impact HRM strategy on systematic thinking.”

Table (10) Multiple Regression Model of the Impact of Strategic Human Resource Management on Systematic Thinking

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.390	.318		4.367	.000		
HRM Strategy	.217	.062	.253	3.520	.00	.745	1.343
R Square							.25
Adjusted R Square							.23
Sig. F Change							0.000
Durbin-Watson							2.13

Impact of strategic human resource management (SHRM) on future vision

Table (11) shows an estimation of regression analysis of the effect of HRM strategy, on future vision which is one dimension of strategic intelligence. The results show that Hence, **H_{03a}** which states that “**There is no significant impact HRM strategy on future vision.**” is rejected.

Table (11) Multiple Regression Model of the Impact of Strategic Human Resource Management on Future Vision

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	2.270	.320		7.083	.000		
HRM Strategy	.391	.062	.462	6.284	.000	.745	1.343
R Square							.21
Adjusted R Square							.20
Sig. F Change							0.000
Durbin-Watson							1.95

Impact of strategic human resource management (SHRM) on motivation

The results in Table (12) provide an analysis of the impact of HRM strategy, on motivation. The results reveal that to reject H_{04a} which states that “There is no significant impact HRM strategy on motivation”.

Table (12) Multiple Regression Model of the Impact of Strategic Human Resource Management on Motivation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.206	.256		4.708	.000		
HRM Strategy	.401	.050	.516	8.075	.000	.745	1.343
R Square							.40
Adjusted R Square							.40
Sig. F Change							0.000
Durbin-Watson							2.10

Conclusion:

The study main goal is to examine the role of human resource management system in the relationship between strategic human resource management and strategic intelligence of Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan. The independent variable is strategic human resource management) and the dependent variable is strategic intelligence which consist of (Systemic Thinking, Future Vision, Motivation)

The study reported that Human capital is the most important resource of the organizations at present, due to the rare characteristics it enjoys, especially its scarcity and the difficulty of simulating or imitating it by the competitors, which is reflected in the monopoly of the organization, and then distinguish them from organizations to others. The study concludes that there is statistical significant role of human resource management system in the relationship between strategic human resource management and strategic intelligence of Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan.

Suggestions:

Jordanian companies must identify the human resources management systems approach aspects that needed to apply, and the ability of these systems to create the competitive advantage of the company in Jordanian pharmaceuticals companies in particular and in Jordanian companies in general. Increase Jordanian company's awareness about strategic intelligence, human resource management system, the strategic human resource management, because of its important in order to achieve the goals and objectives and raise the efficiency of the organization and its effectiveness in the performance of its functions and activities.

Jordanian companies must enhances strategic intelligence functionality across a range of applications such as (Systemic Thinking, Future Vision, Motivation) as this study shows the important of these applications which can apply in any organization.

Jordanian companies must take in consideration when applying Human Resources Information System (HRIS) approach to make a combination of individuals, equipment, and procedures designed to collect, analyse and evaluate, at the first phase and in second phase to distribute accurate and rapid information to the decision-making centres of the organization.

Limitations of the Study

The study has the difficult of the following limitations:

The results of this study may not be generalized over the entire pharmaceutical companies in Jordan, because the study is a case study in Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co. The results of the study limited to these employees where participate on the study.

The study results of role of human resource management system in the relationship between strategic human resource management and strategic intelligence of Al Hikma Pharmaceuticals Co in Jordan. Therefore the results are limit to the variables that used by study.

References:

- Ali, L. (2015). The Importance of Strategic Intelligence in Decision Making A Field Study of the Fertial Foundation. Master Thesis, University of Mohamed Khader, Algeria.
- Borgada, H., and Idris, N. (2015) The Impact of Knowledge Sharing on Human Resources Performance: A Case Study of the Digital TV and Digital Future Unit of the Condor Electronic Foundation in Algeria. Journal of Business Administration. Volume 11, Issue 4.
- Esra N. (2010) the impact of strategic human resource management on organizational performance. Journal of Naval Science and Engineering. 2010, Vol. 6, No.2, pp. 100-116.

- Ismail, P. (2011). Characteristics of Information Systems and their Impact on Determining the Option of Strategic Competition in the Higher and Middle Administrations "An Applied Study on Commercial Banks Operating in the Gaza Strip Master Thesis, Islamic University, Gaza.
- Tesi d. (2010) Human Resource Information Systems and the performance of the Human Resource Function, PhD theses, Libera University, Roma.
- Aboul El Ghanem. (2015). The Effect of Strategic Intelligence on the Effectiveness of Decision Making in Saudi Insurance Companies Operating in the City of Jeddah: An Empirical Study. *Al - Quds Open University Journal for Research and Administrative and Economic Studies*, Volume 2, No. 5, 140-172.
- Ali, L. (2015). The Importance of Strategic Intelligence in Decision Making A Field Study of the Fertial Foundation. Master Thesis, University of Mohamed Khader, Algeria.
- Ali, M., Lei, S., Rehman, A., Anjum, A. (2015) Relationship of Strategic Human Resource Management Practices with Organization Performance and Employee Relation Climate. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, Vol 5(2)39-
- Al-Zu'bi, H. (2016) Aspects of Strategic Intelligence and its Role in Achieving Organizational Agility: An Empirical Investigation. *International Journal of Academic Study in Business and Social Sciences*, Vol. 6, No. 4
- Atta, P. (2015) Strategic intelligence and its impact in determining the strategic option, a survey of the views of a sample of workers in the General Company for Grain Manufacturing of the Ministry of Commerce. *Journal of Baghdad College of Economic Sciences University*, No. 43.
- Imran, N. (2015). Impact of strategic intelligence on organizational innovation. *Journal of the University of Babylon, Pure and Applied Sciences*, No. (3), vol. (23).
- Keikha, A., hadadi, E., Keikha, A. (2016). Investigating effects of Strategic Intelligence of Managers on the performance of employees (Case Study: Private Banks in city of Zahedan). *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Volume 7, Issue 3.
- Sabrina, M. (2015). The Impact of Human Resources Development Strategy on the Performance of Individuals in Universities: Case Study of a Sample of Algerian Universities, Thesis of the University of Mohamed Khaydar Biskra, Algeria.
- Shaikh, M. (2015). HRM Issues in Emerging Economies, the *Business & Management Review*, Volume 5 Number.
- Yahiaoui, N., Anser, A., Lahouel, S. (2015) human resource management and public organizations, *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol.3. No. 2, pp. 1-12.
- Etabi, c. (1991). *Methods of Social Research*, National Library for the printing and publishing, Mosul.
- Litwin, M. (1995). "How to Measure Survey Reliability and Validity". Sage publications, Thousand Oaks
- Sekaran, U. (2003). "Research Methods for Business". 4th edition. John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- Toumi, p. (1971). *Curriculum Social Research*, the House of Culture, Beirut.
- Mansur, h., rahman, a. A. A., shatnawi, a., alfityani, a., almasri, b., & alsaaidh, f. The point of view of tax estimators towards the external auditors: an empirical study from jordan's context (2022)
- Alfityani, a. M. I., & ali, m. A. Impact of disclosure of social responsibility (sr) on the performance of jordanian traditional banks (jtb). (2022).
- Houda aleqadat, et al., (2022). The Influence of Culture and Corporate Governance on Corporate Performance of Jordanian Financial Companies. *17 (05)*, 364-376.

Al-Gasawneh, J. A., Anuar, M. M., Dacko-Pikiewicz, Z., & Saputra, J. (2021). The impact of customer relationship management dimensions on service quality. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 23, 24-44.

Al-Gasawneh, J., Al-Wadi, M., Al-Wadi, B., Alown, B. & Nuseirat, N. (2020). The Interaction Effect of Comprehensiveness Between social media and Online Purchasing Intention in Jordanian Pharmacies. *International Association of Online Engineering*. Retrieved October 13, 2020 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/217794/>.

Al-Gasawneh et al., (2022) Avoiding uncertainty by measuring the impact of perceived risk on the intention to use financial artificial intelligence services, *Uncertain Supply Chain Management* (10).

Alghasawneh, L. A. S., Akhorshaideh, A. H., Alharafsheh, M., Ghasawneh, A., Al-Gasawneh, J. A., & Al-Hadid, A. Y. (2021). Determinants of Supply Chain Management Practices in Jordanian Pharmaceutical Firms. *Solid State Technology*, 64(2), 2986-3001.